

**TERMINOLOGICAL DICTIONARIES
IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE: ISSUES
AND PRINCIPLES OF COMPILATION**

Linguistics

Keywords: lexicography, terminography, lexicography, lexical theory, lexical units, standardization, linguistic dictionaries, multilingual dictionaries, branch dictionaries, typology of dictionaries.

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Abstract

This article discusses lexicography, terminography, and the principles of putting together Uzbek terminological dictionaries. It also goes over the basics of putting together terminological dictionaries. In the compilation of medical dictionaries, the philosophy of lexicography and the theoretical notions of their construction are explored.

Lexicography (lexicography) developed in the early phases of the formation of writing in various peoples as a result of a desire to understand the meaning of some difficult term. The practical importance of dictionaries is dictated by their unique position in society. Dictionary's main functions include studying their own and other languages, describing the mother tongue, standardizing it with the help of annotated, spelling, and similar dictionaries, and establishing the relationship of the mother tongue with other languages using bilingual or multilingual dictionaries, as well as scientific studies of wealth using specific applied research.

On the other hand, linguistics' lexical theory explores the theoretical basis of dictionary categories and their development. The development of the macrostructure of the dictionary: the choice of words, the order of placement of words and dictionary articles, the definition of figurative words, and the inclusion of reference materials in the dictionary, as well as the general typology of dictionaries and the development of new types of dictionaries.

The microstructure of the dictionary, i.e. the development of each dictionary article, grammatical and phonetic interpretation of the word, separation and classification of word meanings, types of illustrations, descriptions, character systems, and word etymology are all problems in theoretical lexicography. [4, pp. 258-259].

Lexicography is a theoretical and practical area founded on the teachings of lexicology, stylistics, phonetics, language history, and grammatical structure. The development of a typology of dictionaries is one of the most important social objectives of modern lexicography. Monolingual lexicography (explanatory dictionaries), bilingual lexicography (dictionaries for translation and language acquisition), and scientific and technical lexicography (terminological dictionaries) are all differentiated in this way.

The aim, function, method of description, and level of coverage of dictionaries all differ. According to the type of description, dictionaries are separated into encyclopedic and philological (linguistic) dictionaries; they can be large, medium, or small in size; and they can be full or short, depending on whether the content coverage is greater or less. [2, pp. 23-24].

The interpretation of an object, a notion, or a concept conveyed in words is the focus of an encyclopedic dictionary. Philological dictionaries are designed to show the meanings of various words as well as their linguistic characteristics. In terms of content, function, and lexicographic description methods, linguistic dictionaries are classified as follows:

- A dictionary that defines or indicates the meanings of words, their extent and amount of use, as well as phonetic and grammatical characteristics;
- A dictionary of foreign words that explains words and terms from another language that have been mastered in one but not in another;
- Dictionaries for translating and interpreting lexical items from one language into another;
- A historical dictionary that shows when words first appeared in the language, as well as the evolution of phonetic, grammatical, and semantic properties;
- Dialectal (dialect) dictionary of terms, particular to the dialects and dialects of the language, demonstrating phonetically and semantically differences from the literary language's vocabulary;
- An etymological dictionary, which shows the word's origin, meaning in the parent language, structure, and changes in sound or meaning;
- A comparative dictionary for comparing and contrasting the vocabulary of languages from the same family, as well as studying the rules of difference between them;
- A spelling dictionary, which keeps track of how words should be spelled according to established norms;
- A dictionary of literary (orthoepic) pronunciations of words;
- A morpheme dictionary that demonstrates the morpheme structure of words in a certain language;
- A phraseological dictionary, which has a vocabulary of phraseological units and stable expressions;
- A frequency dictionary, which shows the number and percentage of times a word is used;
- An inverted (left) dictionary of words with their reverse (after) readings grouped alphabetically;
- A theme (thematic) dictionary contains a list of words separated into categories;
- A dictionary of homonyms, synonyms, antonyms, and paronyms, made up of lexical units such as homonyms, synonyms, antonyms, and paronyms;
- Anthroponymic and toponymic dictionaries, with a lexicon of well-known names and places;
- Terminological dictionaries, which have a lexicon of words and concepts relating to a specific branch of science and technology, a social or economic sphere [6, pp. 130-134].

Because this classification is based solely on philological dictionaries established in Uzbek lexicography, it is likely that additional types of dictionaries exist. The scope and importance of their functions can be linked to the multiplicity of such dictionaries.

The objective of important philological dictionaries is to show the meanings of words and the idiosyncrasies of language. This type of dictionary is further classified into numerous categories based on the manner of word description, descriptive material, and dictionary function.

The main focus of this research is on the terminological dictionaries described in the preceding classification of dictionary types. As a consequence of study in the field of terminological lexicography (terminography), such dictionaries hold a unique place in the evolution of the relevant discipline, as they represent the state of development of a field at a particular time and the existing concepts in the field. Depending on the presentation and interpretation of the dictionary, such dictionaries have characteristics of both encyclopedic and philological dictionaries; they may be in one, two, or more languages, annotated, unexplained, and encyclopedic in nature.

Terminological dictionaries are useful not only for a certain branch of knowledge, but also for regulating, improving, and standardizing terminology [1, p. 3]. The most fundamental and comprehensive source of information for both industry representatives and other audiences utilizing the dictionary is terminological dictionaries prepared by professionals in the relevant subject. Because terminological dictionaries, as well as the descriptions and explanations supplied for the terms in them, are based on the notion of representing all aspects of the concept, they are prepared by experts. As a result, these dictionaries represent the most important foundation for the industry. The importance of specialist dictionaries is demonstrated by the fact that any discipline of knowledge grows in the context of time and space, and these processes are mirrored in dictionaries.

As part of the general lexicon, terminological lexicon is an important object for creating terminological dictionaries and performing ongoing in-depth study in relevant disciplines of science. After all, it reflects or, on the other hand, serves the development of the industry. In Uzbek medical terminology, as well as any other field, such dictionaries are accessible. The history of these has been briefly addressed in earlier sections.

Terminology of scientific and technology concepts is done in collaboration with linguists who are experts in specific domains. This process, as a scientific study, is mirrored in terminological dictionaries first and foremost. The term, as a lexical unit belonging to a limited lexical layer, is a significant resource for research in a certain topic. While lexicology is concerned with the study of literary language's lexical units, lexicography is concerned with the theory and practice of gathering, classifying, and describing these lexical units, and therefore organizing dictionaries. Terminology is a branch of science concerned with the study of specific lexical units.

Linguists and professionals refer to terminological study as "terminological lexicography," "scientific and technical lexicography," and the reflection of terminological units in dictionaries as "terminological lexicography." Linguists proposed using the term terminography instead of compound nouns in the last part of the twentieth century. Indeed, the proposed term can be used to describe functional identity and can be used interchangeably with the term lexicography. According to linguists, this phrase refers to the theory and practice of building particular and terminological dictionaries [5, p. 5].

Given that the term can convey one of the meanings of terminology and perform one of its purposes, its capacity to fully and briefly name the process in terms of the function it performs while remaining concise suggests that it is ready and appropriate for usage in practice.

Terminography, then, is concerned with the construction of terminological dictionaries, as well as theoretical and practical aspects of terminographic work.

A terminological or special dictionary is a sort of encyclopedic dictionary that contains, interprets, and explains terms related to a certain field of study.

Terminological dictionaries can also interpret terms in only one discipline, or they might cover a number of related knowledge terms that aren't too far away from the topic.

Monolingual dictionaries, developed by summarizing phrases in one language and interpreting them in that language, or bilingual, trilingual, and multilingual dictionaries, based on alternatives and interpretations of terms in one or more languages.

Many similar terminological investigations may be found in the subject of medicine, in particular. "Russian – Latin – Uzbek Explanatory Dictionary of Medical Terms," for example.

Terminological dictionaries cover the terminological units of a specific industry within a specific time period, and obsolete industry terminology is rarely utilized.

As synchronous materials become obsolete, however, this terminographic work retains its value as a resource for researching the history of pertinent terminology as well as the diachronic state of the language on which these terminological dictionaries are based.

Terminology work is an important aspect of lexicography in general.

Despite the fact that most terminographic processes are similar to lexicographic processes, they differ in numerous ways.

A terminological unit's definition, description, and classification, for example, are considerably different from lexical units' definition, description, and classification in a common language.

Based on the Moscow Committee for Technical Terminology's "Note for Workers on the Regulation of Scientific and Technical Terminology," well-known lexicographer S.Akobirov developed recommendations for conducting terminological research and compiling terminological dictionaries and described the process in six stages [3, pp. 13-14].

S.V.Grinyov demonstrates and interprets these stages as four [5, p. 11-13], based on terminologists' perspectives on the stages and how the process should be carried out sequentially in the building of a terminological dictionary.

The type of dictionary and its primary elements are chosen early on in the process of producing a terminological dictionary. The lexical units are then gathered. Only terms, i.e. words and phrases constructed to clearly represent certain concepts or to reflect specific objects, are normally chosen in this procedure, though nomenclature units may be included.

The units chosen for the dictionary, as well as the terms included in it, are evaluated in depth in the third stage; each is discussed separately.

The language chosen for the dictionary is analyzed, classified, and explained differently in this situation, depending on the dictionary's purpose and function.

The semantic relations between these lexical units - hierarchical and associative relations - are defined, these links are detailed in the dictionary article or a foreign language equivalent is chosen if necessary, and the grammatical aspects of the stated terminological units are presented.

Each dictionary article's content and structure are defined, as well as the primary and secondary indications.

The results of the terminological work will be compiled into a dictionary, edited, and the introduction section will be written and submitted for publication in the final stage.

The lexicographer treats the term primarily as a word in broad philological (translated and annotated) dictionaries, interpreting it according to the universal meanings of the word and confining the term to the most important and fundamental characteristics of the notion.

In explanatory terminological dictionaries, terms are viewed as a unit of interpretation of existing concepts in a specific field, and the interpretation of terms is done from an encyclopedic standpoint, with the term definition containing all important features of the concept represented by this nominative unit.

As a result, terminological dictionaries are mostly compiled by professionals in the relevant discipline, leaving the linguistic features unique to the lexical unit practically unnoticed.

Although the construction of terminographic works in line with the above processes enhanced the quality of terminological dictionaries by industry in the second half of the last century, the sequence of these steps is not always followed.

The truth of S.F.Akobirov's assertion may be observed in the sectorial terminological dictionaries published at the period, particularly medical dictionaries.

It's worth noting that modern Uzbek jargon dates from the 1920s.

N.Turakulov released the first terminographic dictionary on the socio-political domain in the Arabic alphabet in 1922.

More than 250 terminological dictionaries have been created in more than 50 different fields and branches of science and technology since the beginning of this year [7, p. 54-67]. (About 300 years ago – A.S.) Medical terminological dictionaries account for a large portion of the total.

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